

ISic3627

I.Sicily inscription 3627

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

incisa sulla parete rocciosa di un ipogeo della necropoli scavata nella cosiddetta collina dei Gesuiti a Ghzira, presso Marsa

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140930

1. κοιμητήριον
2. ἡγορασμένον
3. ἀπὸ Ζωσιμῆ-
4. τινος καὶ Ἄντι-
5. κ [ήτου — —]
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285162

EDCS 39101550

PHI 140930

Bibliography

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